

Reverse Logistics Practices and Organizational Resilience of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria

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The study assessed the nexus between Reverse Logistics Practices (dimensioned by returns/exchanges, and repairs/replacements) and organisational resilience (measured by robustness and flexibility) of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria. The Dynamic Capabilities Theory provided theoretical foundation for the study which was underpinned by the positivism philosophical paradigm. The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey approach, with a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale. The target population was 194 maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria which are registered with the Nigerian Port Authority. However, the elements of the accessible population were restricted to 950 management staff drawn from the 98 maritime logistic companies located in Rivers, Delta and Cross River States with the presence of ports activities. The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was utilised to determine a sample size of 274 respondents, and the simple random sampling was adopted with the aid of random numbers. Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The study found that while returns and exchanges contributed positively and significantly to the robustness of these companies, their influence on flexibility was limited and negative. Similarly, repairs and replacements showed a weak positive link with robustness but do not significantly enhance flexibility. Overall, the results underscore the importance of enhancing specific reverse logistics practices to improve organizational resilience. Therefore, it was recommended that Managers of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria should optimize their returns and exchanges processes to strengthen their robustness further. This could involve effectively managing returns and exchanges to minimize costs and customer dissatisfaction. Furthermore, Managers of maritime logistics companies should enhance the adoption of repairs and replacements strategies in order to increase their robustness abilities, by establishing efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.

Keywords: Reverse Logistics Practices, theoretical foundation, positivism philosophical paradigm.

INTRODUCTION

Maritime logistics companies play a crucial role in Nigeria's economic development, facilitating international trade, supporting the oil and gas sector, and contributing to job creation. These companies are essential in moving

goods and commodities, with about 90% of global trade carried out via seaborne transport (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018). Nigeria, as Africa's largest economy, depends on maritime logistics for crude oil exports, which account for over 80% of its export earnings (Nwanosike & Ikegbunam, 2019). Additionally, the industry supports offshore drilling activities and the transport of petroleum products, making it vital for the oil and gas sector (Obiora et al., 2020).

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Maritime logistics also creates employment opportunities, aiding in economic development (Akinwale et al., 2019). However, the sector faces challenges such as poor infrastructure, leading to port congestion, operational inefficiencies, and delays (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018). Security concerns also threaten operations, increasing costs and risks for the companies (Obiora et al., 2020). Moreover, regulatory bottlenecks and complex customs procedures hinder smooth operations, while environmental sustainability issues add further challenges as companies struggle to meet international regulations (Akinwale et al., 2019).

These challenges lead to weak level of organisational resilience of Nigeria's maritime logistics sector. As businesses face increasing challenges, such as technological advancements, market volatility, and global crises, resilience becomes vital for long-term success. Resilient organisations can better mitigate risks and seize opportunities, enabling them to recover faster and maintain competitiveness (Burnard & Bhamra, 2019). This resilience also fosters a culture of continuous improvement, which is essential in an ever-changing business environment (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011). Organisational resilience refers to an organisation's ability to anticipate, prepare for, respond to, and adapt to disruptions and incremental changes in order to survive and thrive. It goes beyond merely bouncing back from adversity; it involves learning from disruptions and emerging stronger. Ultimately, organisational resilience is key to surviving and thriving in today's volatile business landscape (Duchek, 2020). Measures of organisational resilience include: operational continuity (Duchek, 2020); rapid recovery time (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011); as well as learning and adaptation (Burnard & Bhamra, 2019). This study adopts robustness and flexibility as measures of organizational resilience (Chu, 2015; Kantur & Iseri-Say, 2015). Moreso, predictors of organizational resilience include: Effective leadership (Hillmann & Guenther, 2021); collaboration, innovation, and flexibility (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011); resourcefulness and flexibility (Duchek, 2020); strategic planning and risk management (Burnard & Bhamra, 2019). However, this study adopts reverse logistics practices (dimensioned by returns and exchanges, as well as repairs and replacements), as the predictor of organizational resilience. Therefore, this study sought to establish the link between reverse logistics practices and organisational resilience of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem of this study is weak level of organisational resilience of maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria. These companies exhibit several manifestations of weak organisational resilience, such as: operational

inefficiency (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018); extended recovery times after disruptions (Akinwale et al., 2019); poor crisis management and decision-making (Ogundana et al., 2021); lack of adaptive strategies (Obiora et al., 2020); limited collaboration and communication (Ekwueme & Ofoegbu, 2019). The weak organisational resilience of maritime logistics companies can be traced to several underlying causes, which include: inadequate infrastructure (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018); poor risk management, contingency planning, leadership and decision-making challenges (Akinwale et al., 2019)). The effects of weak organisational resilience in maritime logistics companies are substantial, and include operational inefficiency, prolonged downtime, reduced competitiveness and long-term financial instability (Ogundana et al., 2021; Obiora et al., 2020). Suggested solutions to the problem of weak organisational resilience include: infrastructure development, leadership development, robust risk management frameworks, enhancing collaboration and partnerships, developing a learning culture and enhanced security measures (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018; Akinwale et al., 2019; Ogundana et al., 2021; Ekwueme and Ofoegbu, 2019; Akinwale et al., 2019).

Suggested solutions to the problem of weak organisational resilience include: infrastructure development, leadership development, robust risk management frameworks, enhancing collaboration and partnerships, developing a learning culture and enhanced security measures (Onwuegbuchunam, 2018; Akinwale et al., 2019; Ogundana et al., 2021; Ekwueme and Ofoegbu, 2019; Akinwale et al., 2019). Other proffered solutions include resourcefulness and flexibility (Duchek, 2020). Despite the avalanche of suggested solutions, the challenge of weak organisational resilience still persists within maritime logistics companies in South-South, Nigeria. This suggests a contextual gap in literature. Therefore, this study sought to close the gap in literature by critically examining reverse logistics and how it relates to organizational resilience of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the relationship between returns/exchanges, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the relationship between returns/exchanges, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the nexus between repairs/replacements, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

Assess the relationship between repairs/replacements, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

The research questions are as follows:

- i. What is the relationship between returns/exchanges, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between returns/exchanges, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- iii. What is the relationship between repairs/replacements, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?
- iv. What is the relationship between repairs/replacements, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria?

returns/exchanges, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between returns/exchanges, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant link repairs/replacements, and robustness of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between repairs/replacements, and flexibility of maritime logistic companies in South-South Nigeria.

The formulated null hypotheses are:

H₀₁: There is no significant link between

Conceptual Framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Reverse Logistics Practices and Organisational Resilience.

Source: Conceptualised by the Researcher. Dimensions of reverse logistics practices were adopted from Ghiani and Manni (2023) while the measures of organisational resilience were adopted from Kantur and Iseri-Say (2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reverse Logistics Practices: Reverse logistics refers to the process of moving goods from their final destination back to the manufacturer or distribution point for proper disposal, recycling, refurbishment, or remanufacturing (Zhang et al., 2021). It encompasses a broad range of activities, including returns, exchanges, repairs, and the management of products at the end of their lifecycle. Reverse logistics practices are critical in reducing waste, optimizing resource use, and improving customer satisfaction by efficiently handling returns and defective products (Agrawal, Singh, & Murtaza, 2023).

Returns and Exchanges: Returns and exchanges involve the process of customers sending back products

due to upgrades, reuse, dissatisfaction, defects, or incorrect deliveries (Mao, Chen, & Li, 2020). Returns management requires companies to develop systems for inspecting, restocking, or disposing of goods, depending on their condition. Effective management of returns and exchanges can reduce costs, increase customer retention, and maintain a positive brand image ((Hassan, Daghfous, & Huscroft, 2021).

Repairs and Replacements: Repairs and replacements refer to processes where defective products are either fixed or substituted with new ones to meet customer expectations (Jabbour et al., 2020). Offering repairs or replacements can help companies retain customers while managing the costs associated with product failures. In reverse logistics, repairs also offer opportunities to

refurbish and resell products, thus recovering some of the product's value (Boukherroub et al., 2022).

Organisational Resilience: Organisational resilience is the capacity of a company to withstand disruptions and maintain operations under adverse conditions (Yu et al., 2019). In reverse logistics, resilience plays a vital role as businesses must manage fluctuating returns, repair demands, and supply chain disruptions efficiently (Ivanov, 2021). Companies that build resilience into their reverse logistics systems are better equipped to respond to unexpected changes, ensuring continuity in their supply chain operations.

Robustness: Robustness refers to the ability of a logistics system to operate efficiently despite changes or disruptions in the external environment (Liu et al., 2022). A robust system can handle variations in return volumes, repair demands, and product recalls without significant impact on overall operations. This ensures stability in processes and minimizes operational disruptions, even in times of supply chain uncertainty (Gunasekaran, Subramanian, & Papadopoulos, 2022).

Flexibility: Flexibility enables companies to adapt their systems and processes to changing market conditions, return volumes, and customer expectations (Narayanamurthy, Deshmukh, & Vasthimal, 2021). A flexible logistics system can respond quickly to fluctuations in demand for repairs, replacements, and returns, ensuring timely delivery and satisfaction of customer requirements (Yin et al., 2022).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997) provided theoretical foundation for this study. The theory explains how firms adapt, integrate, and reconfigure internal and external resources to address rapidly changing environments and sustain competitive advantage. This theory is highly relevant to the reverse logistics practices and organisational resilience of maritime logistics companies. In the context of reverse logistics, dynamic capabilities enable these companies to manage complex processes such as returns, repairs, and recycling, by continuously upgrading their systems and optimizing resource utilization (Zhu & Sarkis, 2019). Moreover, dynamic capabilities are critical for building resilience, allowing companies to adapt to disruptions like fluctuating demand or infrastructure challenges, and ensuring operational continuity (Wang, Craighead, & Li, 2020).

Empirical Reviews

Zhang and Chen (2021) conducted a study examining the relationship between reverse logistics practices and organizational performance in manufacturing firms across

Southeast Asia. Their study encompassed a population of 200 manufacturing firms, with a sample of 150 firms. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), they found that reverse logistics practices significantly enhanced organizational efficiency, cost savings, and customer satisfaction. Agrawal et al. (2023) explored the impact of reverse logistics on resilience within the supply chains of logistics companies in India. The study involved 300 logistics firms, with data collected from a sample of 180 companies.

Through regression analysis, the researchers found that organizational resilience was enhanced by robustness and flexibility in reverse logistics practices. Mao, Li, and Chen (2020) investigated returns management within the retail sector in China and its contributions to organizational sustainability. The study surveyed 500 retail firms, using a sample of 200 firms, and applied Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to interpret the data. Findings indicated that effective management of returns and exchanges provided sustainability benefits, especially through resource recovery processes. Hassan and Huscroft (2021) examined the role of digitalization in reverse logistics and its effect on resilience in U.S.-based e-commerce companies. With a population of 250 firms and a sample of 130, the study used correlation and regression analyses to conclude that digitalizing reverse logistics operations significantly improved organizational resilience by enhancing flexibility and responsiveness to market changes. Wang, Craighead, and Li (2020) explored dynamic capabilities and their influence on organizational resilience in Chinese logistics firms.

Their study, conducted with a sample of 120 firms from a population of 150, used SEM to reveal that dynamic capabilities such as adaptability and effective resource allocation bolster resilience. Narayanamurthy et al. (2021) focused on how flexibility in reverse logistics practices contributes to resilience during disruptions in South Asian supply chains. Surveying 100 companies with a sample size of 75, they used multivariate regression analysis to show that flexibility in reverse logistics processes significantly enhanced resilience, particularly in volatile markets. Boukherroub et al. (2022) investigated the role of robustness in reverse logistics within global food supply chains and its contribution to sustainability and resilience. From a population of 200 logistics companies, they analyzed data from 150 firms using qualitative content analysis. The findings demonstrated that robust reverse logistics practices helped maintain sustainability and protect supply chains from disruptions.

Moreso, Adewole and Musa (2022) examined the impact of reverse logistics on organizational resilience in Nigerian maritime logistics firms. They employed a descriptive survey approach with a sample of 200 respondents from six major logistics companies in Lagos. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the study found that reverse logistics activities, such as recycling,

Table 1 Methodological Analysis of Response Rate

ACTIVITIES	NUMBER OF OCCURRANCES	PERCENTAGE OF OCCURRANCES
Copies of Questionnaire administered	274	100.00
Copies of Questionnaire retrieved	230	83.94
Copies of Questionnaire not retrieved	44	16.06
Copies of Questionnaire completed but not usable	28	10.22
Copies of Questionnaire completed and usable	202	73.72

Source: Fieldwork data result, 2024.

repair, and reuse, positively influenced resilience by reducing costs and providing alternative revenue streams ($\beta = 0.62$, $p < 0.05$). The study highlighted that integrating reverse logistics into operations significantly improves resilience, enabling firms to withstand supply chain disruptions. Furtherstill, Obi and Nwosu (2023) explored the effect of reverse logistics strategies on the operational flexibility of maritime logistics companies in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A sample of 120 respondents was drawn from a population of 180 employees across four logistics companies. Data were analyzed using regression analysis, revealing that reverse logistics practices, including returns management and remanufacturing, contributed to enhanced flexibility and rapid response capabilities in volatile market conditions ($\text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.58$, $p < 0.05$).

The study emphasized that effective reverse logistics processes are crucial for building adaptive resilience within maritime logistics operations. Likewise, Ibrahim and Abdulrahman (2023) investigated the role of reverse logistics in enhancing the supply chain resilience of port logistics companies in Delta State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional research design was adopted, and 250 logistics personnel were surveyed using structured questionnaires. Through multiple regression analysis, the study found that reverse logistics activities, particularly recycling and redistribution, significantly improved supply chain resilience by increasing the agility of logistics networks ($\text{Adj.}R^2 = 0.67$, $F(4, 246) = 10.532$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that reverse logistics practices are essential for maritime firms to navigate supply chain disruptions effectively.

Furthermore, Owolabi and Adebayo (2024) conducted a study on the influence of reverse logistics technology adoption on resilience in Nigerian shipping companies. The researchers surveyed a sample of 140 logistics managers from a population of 200 companies in Warri, using a combination of SEM and correlation analysis for data interpretation. The findings indicated that adopting digital solutions in reverse logistics, such as real-time tracking and automated sorting, significantly enhanced resilience by improving response times and operational efficiency ($\beta = 0.74$, $p < 0.01$). The study recommended that maritime logistics firms in Nigeria invest in digital technologies to strengthen their resilience against

market disruptions and improve supply chain responsiveness.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The cross-sectional survey was adopted, while the underlying philosophy for this study is positivism.

Population of the Study: The target population was 194 maritime logistic companies in South-South, Nigeria which are registered with the Nigerian Port Authority. However, the elements of the accessible population were restricted to 950 management staff drawn from the 98 maritime logistic companies located in Rivers, Delta and Cross River States with the presence of ports activities.

Sample and Sampling Technique: The Krejcie and Morgan's formula was utilized to determine a sample size of 274 respondents, and the simple random sampling was adopted.

Method of Data Collection: This study adopted a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale.

Method of Data Analysis: Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

Decision Rule: This study relied on the Cronbach's Alpha 0.7 reliability threshold for all the constructs, as recommended by several scholars (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hair et al., 2014). Also, for a two tailed test, $t\text{-values} > 1.96$ and $p\text{-values} < 0.05$ are significant, while $t\text{-values} < 1.96$ and $p\text{-values} > 0.05$ are non-significant (Hair et al., 2014).

As indicated in table 1, a total of 274 copies of the questionnaire were administered, out of which a total of 230 copies were retrieved, representing 83.94% of actual distribution rate. However, 44 copies representing 16.06% were not retrieved, as the concerned respondents could not create time to complete them, despite the fact that the researcher embarked on several visits, sent emails and made phone calls as reminders. Of the 230 copies of the instrument retrieved, 28 copies, representing 10.22% were not usable due to missing responses. This is in line with Kline (1998), who posited

Table 1 Gender of Respondents

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	143	70.79	62.2	62.2
	Female	59	29.21	37.8	100.0
	Total	202	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 Age of Respondents

		Age of respondents			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 - 29	37	18.3	18.3	18.3
	30 - 39	88	43.5	43.5	61.7
	40 - 49	51	25.2	25.2	87.0
	50 - 59	21	10.4	10.4	97.4
	60 and above	5	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	202	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Educational qualification of respondents

		Educational Qualification			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	WAEC/SSCE/NECO	23	10.0	10.0	13.9
	NCE/OND	11	4.8	4.8	18.7
	HND/ BSc	107	46.5	46.5	81.7
	M.Sc./MBA	35	15.2	15.2	97.0
	Ph.D	7	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	202	100.0	100.0	

that only cases with complete records or equivalent number of cases, are included in order to maintain consistency, using a case-wise deletion method. Overall, 230 (83.94%) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, while 202 (73.72%) were found to be usable.

From table 1, the result shows that where the frequency for the male, $n = 143$ (70.79%), the frequency for the female, $n = 59$ (29.21%). The results suggest a highly male dominant organization and possibly the industry as well. The implications could follow several assumptions given the significance of the disparity in the gender distribution. One could pin-point such disparity to possible inequalities existent in the societal systems which probably emphasize on certain role functions, or even possible patriarchal systems or cultures wherein males are afforded better opportunities rather than the female. Conversely, one might also argue that such disparities might also exist due to the nature of competition and aggressiveness inherent within the maritime logistics industry in South-South, Nigeria and with the female preferring a safer and less rigorous or engaging domain.

From table 2, The result on the distribution for the age of the respondents demonstrates that a high proportion of the respondents are between the ages of 30-39 with a

high percentage of 43.5% while the next group with high proportion of the respondents are between the ages of 40-49, representing 25.2% of the respondents. Generally, the results suggest a stronger presence of workers within their 30s and 40s as being substantially dominant with regards to other age categories within the organization. However, the age group for a younger set (aged between 20 and 29) of respondents has a frequency of $n = 37$, followed by that of an older group of between 50-59, at $n = 21$; the lowest frequency occurs at the age group of 60 years and above with $n = 5$. The evidence also indicates possible consistency or stability in the choice of recruitment age, and reflects possible policy on the working age in maritime logistics companies in South South, Nigeria.

Table 3, revealed that the majority of the respondents which are 107 representing 46.5% are HND/B.Sc. holders. Interestingly, 35 respondents (15.2%) have M.Sc./MBA degrees while respondents (3%) are holders of Ph.D degree. The implication is that a large proportion of the respondents are well education and may possess higher levels of abstract thinking which would have enabled them to easily understand and respond appropriately to the questionnaire. While 23 respondents (10%) attained secondary education, the majority of

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics (UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
RETURNS AND EXCHANGES							
1) Our organization effectively manages returns and exchanges to minimize costs and customer dissatisfaction.	202	15.88	4.147	.077	.244	-.695	.483
2) In our firms, we have established efficient processes and systems for handling product returns and exchanges.	202	2.98	1.184	-.074	.244	-.936	.483
3) In our company, customer returns and exchanges are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.	202	3.05	1.078	.401	.244	-.712	.483
4) In our organisation, we actively analyze and learn from return and exchange data to identify opportunities for improvement.	202	3.37	1.161	-.235	.244	-.611	.483
5) In our organisation, we actively analyze and learn from return and exchange data to identify opportunities for improvement.	202	3.48	1.177	-.124	.244	-1.090	.483
5) Our organization provides clear and transparent return and exchange policies to customers.	202	3.00	1.407	.000	.244	-1.281	.483
6) Overall, our returns and exchanges processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.	202	3.65	1.026	-.365	.244	-.737	.483
REPAIRS AND REPLACEMENTS							
1. Our organization effectively manages repairs and replacements to minimize downtime and costs.	202	17.53	4.732	.243	.244	-.076	.483
2. We have established efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.	202	2.82	1.115	-.037	.244	-.461	.483
2. We have established efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.	202	2.91	.898	.183	.244	.277	.483
3. Product repairs and replacements are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.	202	2.87	1.042	-.064	.244	-.449	.483
4. We actively analyze and learn from repair and replacement data to identify opportunities for improvement.	202	2.87	1.042	-.064	.244	-.449	.483
4. We actively analyze and learn from repair and replacement data to identify opportunities for improvement.	202	2.91	1.194	.180	.244	-.767	.483
5. Our organization provides timely and reliable repair and replacement services to customers.	202	2.86	1.175	.206	.244	-.649	.483
6. Overall, our repairs and replacements processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.	202	3.17	1.293	-.097	.244	-1.093	.483
ROBUSTNESS							
1) Our company does not give up and continues its path.	202	20.21	4.832	.278	.244	-.417	.483
2) Our company stands straight and preserves its position.	202	3.24	1.167	-.017	.244	-.987	.483
2) Our company stands straight and preserves its position.	202	3.35	1.159	.138	.244	-1.158	.483
3) Our company is successful in generating diverse solutions	202	3.05	1.078	.401	.244	-.712	.483
4) Our company shows resistance to the end in order not to lose.	202	2.91	1.194	.180	.244	-.767	.483
FLEXIBILITY							
1) Our company is flexible in allocating marketing resources to market a diverse line of products.	202	15.83	4.708	.013	.244	-1.055	.483
1. Our company is flexible in allocating marketing resources to market a diverse line of products.	202	2.63	1.107	.122	.244	-.746	.483
2. Our company is flexible in allocating production resources to manufacture a broad range of product.	202	3.05	1.170	.294	.244	-.836	.483
3. Our company is flexible in product design to support a broad range of potential product.	202	3.43	1.520	-.419	.244	-1.311	.483

4. Our company has an ability to adapt our product strategies to match products/ services with targeted market segment.	202	3.40	1.412	-.382	.244	-1.129	.483
5. Our company redeploys organizational resources effectively to support our firm's intended strategies.	202	3.32	1.051	-.234	.244	-.398	.483
6. Our company modifies the resources we can use in developing, manufacturing, and delivering its	202	3.12	1.038	-.024	.244	-.585	.483

Source: SPSS output of Research Data (2024)

Figure 2: Measurement (Outer) Model
Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

respondent still have post-secondary education and this reflect a deliberate effort by the owners of maritime logistics companies in South South, Nigeria, to hire most graduates.

Table 4, shows the descriptive statistics for the study on *Reverse Logistics Practices and Organizational Resilience of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria*. For *Returns*

and Exchanges, the mean score of 15.88 suggests a generally positive perception, with individual items ranging from 2.98 to 3.65. Skewness values for this construct are close to

Table 5: Result for Reflective Measurement Models (CONVERGENT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY)

Constructs	Items	Convergent Validity			Internal Consistency Reliability			
		Path coefficient (β)	Indicator Reliability (β^2)	AVE	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)	Effect sizes (f^2)	Predictive Accuracy (R^2)	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
RETURNS AND EXCHANGES	1) Our organization effectively manages returns and exchanges to minimize costs and customer dissatisfaction.	0.830	0.689	0.560	0.928	2.760	0.734	0.904
	2) In our firms, we have established efficient processes and systems for handling product returns and exchanges.	0.894	0.799					
	3) In our company, customer returns and exchanges are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.	0.832	0.692					
	4) In our organisation, we actively analyze and learn from return and exchange data to identify opportunities for improvement.	0.866	0.750					
	5) Our organization provides clear and transparent return and exchange policies to customers.	Deleted	Deleted					
	6) Overall, our returns and exchanges processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.	0.825	0.681					
REPAIRS AND REPLACEMENTS	1. Our organization effectively manages repairs and replacements to minimize downtime and costs.	0.695	0.483	0.636	0.868	2.154	0.683	0.856
	2. We have established efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.	0.832	0.692					
	3. Product repairs and replacements are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.	0.832	0.692					
	4. We actively analyze and learn from repair and replacement data to identify opportunities for improvement.	0.856	0.733					
	5. Our organization provides timely and reliable repair and replacement services to customers.	0.763	0.582					
	6. Overall, our repairs and replacements processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.	Deleted	Deleted					

ROBUSTNESS	1) Our company does not give up and continues its path.	0.656	0.430	0.642	0.876	2.140	0.682	0.821
	2) Our company stands straight and preserves its position.	0.817	0.667					
	3) Our company is successful in generating diverse solutions	0.900	0.810					
	4) Our company shows resistance to the end in order not to lose.	0.813	0.661					
FLEXIBILITY	1. Our company is flexible in allocating marketing resources to market a diverse line of products.	0.865	0.748	0.567	0.885	5.230	0.839	0.845
	2. Our company is flexible in allocating production resources to manufacture a broad range of product.	0.838	0.702					
	3. Our company is flexible in product design to support a broad range of potential product.	0.586	0.343					
	4. Our company has an ability to adapt our product strategies to match products/ services with targeted market segment.	0.596	0.355					
	5. Our company redeploys organizational resources effectively to support our firm's intended strategies.	0.779	0.607					
	6. Our company modifies the resources we can use in developing, manufacturing, and delivering its	0.805	0.648					

Source: SmartPLS4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

Table 6: DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

	FLEXIBILITY	REPAIRS_AND_REPLACEMENTS	RETURNS_AND_EXCHANGES	ROBUSTNESS
FLEXIBILITY	0.790			
REPAIRS_AND_REPLACEMENTS	0.734	0.798		
RETURNS_AND_EXCHANGES	0.753	0.619	0.850	
ROBUSTNESS	0.761	0.716	0.801	0.822

Source: SmartPLS4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

Figure 3: Structural Model showing the beta values and p-values
Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Figure 4: Structural Model showing the beta values and t-values.
Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Table 7 : Results of Hypotheses Testing

Null Hypo.	Stages	Path Coefficients (β)	R ²	T Statistics (t) ≥ 1.96	P Values (p) < 0.05	Decision on Null Hypotheses
H ₀₁	RETEX→ROBUST	0.484 (Weak)	0.692 Moderate	4.158 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported
H ₀₂	RETEX→FLEX	-0.050 (Weak)	0.630 Moderate	0.531 (Not Significant)	0.596 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₃	REPREP→ROBUST	0.288 (Weak)	0.596 Moderate	4.330 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported
H ₀₄	REPREP→FLEX	0.125 (Weak)	0.549 Moderate	1.889 (Not Significant)	0.059 (Not Significant)	Supported

Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

zero, indicating a fairly symmetric distribution, while kurtosis values are mostly negative, suggesting slightly flatter distributions. In *Repairs and Replacements*, the mean score of 17.53 aligns with moderate agreement, and skewness remains minimal, showing a nearly symmetric distribution across items. Kurtosis values in this area hover near zero, implying an approximately normal distribution. For the *Organizational Resilience* constructs, *Robustness* and *Flexibility* have mean scores of 20.21 and 15.83, respectively, indicating moderate-to-high resilience levels. Skewness for *Robustness* is slightly positive (0.278), while *Flexibility* has near-zero skewness, indicating close-to-symmetric response distributions. Kurtosis for both resilience constructs is negative, particularly for *Flexibility* (-1.055), showing flatter-than-normal distributions. Examining the dataset's normality, skewness values near zero suggest a mostly symmetric distribution for most items, indicating normality in the responses. However, the consistently negative kurtosis values, especially for *Returns and Exchanges* and *Flexibility*, indicate distributions that are flatter than the normal bell curve.

Figure 2, and table 5 reveals that the reflective measurement model assessment for *Reverse Logistics Practices* and *Organizational Resilience* of maritime logistics companies demonstrates robust convergent validity and reliability across constructs, with all measures (Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, AVE) exceeding recommended thresholds. For *Returns and Exchanges*, path coefficients range from 0.825 to 0.894, an AVE of 0.560, composite reliability of 0.928, and a substantial R² of 0.734, with a large effect size (f² = 2.760). *Repairs and Replacements* also show strong reliability ($\alpha = 0.856$, $\rho_c = 0.868$), an AVE of 0.636, moderate predictive accuracy (R² = 0.683), and a high effect size (f² = 2.154). *Robustness* achieves an AVE of 0.642, high reliability ($\rho_c = 0.876$, $\alpha = 0.821$), moderate predictive accuracy (R² = 0.682), and a large effect size (f² = 2.140). *Flexibility* has the highest predictive accuracy

(R² = 0.839) and a very large effect size (f² = 5.230), with an AVE of 0.567 and excellent reliability ($\rho_c = 0.885$, $\alpha = 0.845$). Overall, the AVE values confirm that each construct has more than half of its indicators' variance explained, ensuring adequate convergent validity and robust reliability with cronbach's alpha coefficients greater than the 0.7 cut-off point.

As revealed in table 3, reveals the discriminant validity assessment of Reverse Logistics Practices and Organizational Resilience constructs in maritime logistics companies confirms distinctiveness across constructs, as shown by the Fornell-Larcker criterion. Each construct's square root of AVE exceeds its correlations with other constructs, verifying discriminant validity. Specifically, Flexibility has an AVE square root of 0.790, which is higher than its correlations with Repairs and Replacements (0.734), Returns and Exchanges (0.753), and Robustness (0.761). Repairs and Replacements has an AVE square root of 0.798, exceeding correlations with Flexibility (0.734), Returns and Exchanges (0.619), and Robustness (0.716). Similarly, Returns and Exchanges shows an AVE square root of 0.850, greater than its correlations with Flexibility (0.753), Repairs and Replacements (0.619), and Robustness (0.801). Lastly, Robustness has an AVE square root of 0.822, which is also higher than its correlations with Flexibility (0.761), Repairs and Replacements (0.716), and Returns and Exchanges (0.801). These findings confirm that each construct has evidence of discriminant validity and uniquely represents its concept within Reverse Logistics Practices and Organizational Resilience.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Returns/Exchanges and Robustness: From figures 3 and 4, and table 7, the results of the hypothesis (H₀₁) test revealed that there is a moderate positive and significant relationship between

returns/exchanges and robustness of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria, with a β value of 0.484, indicating that Returns/Exchanges moderately influence Robustness. The t-value of 4.158 exceeds the 1.96 threshold for a two-tailed test at the 0.05 significance level, and a p-value of 0.000 confirms statistical significance, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis and affirm a significant link. The R^2 value of 0.692 suggests that Returns/Exchanges explain 69.2% of the variance in Robustness. This is not a surprise finding as it agrees with Zhang and Chen (2021) who found that reverse logistics practices significantly enhanced organizational efficiency, cost savings, and customer satisfaction.

Relationship between Returns/Exchanges and Flexibility: From figures 3 and 4, and table 7, the results of the hypothesis (H_{02}) test indicated a weak negative and no significant relationship between returns/exchanges and flexibility in Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South, Nigeria, with path coefficient (β) of -0.050 suggesting a negligible and slightly negative correlation, and implying that Returns/Exchanges do not meaningfully influence Flexibility. Additionally, the t-value of 0.531 is well below the 1.96 threshold for significance and the p-value of 0.596 exceeds 0.05, leading us to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}). Although the R^2 value of 0.630 indicates that 63% of the variance in Flexibility is explained by the model. However, this finding is surprising as it disagrees with Agrawal et al. (2023) who found that organizational resilience was enhanced by robustness and flexibility in reverse logistics practices.

Relationship between Repairs/Replacements and Robustness: From figures 3 and 4, and table 7, the results of the hypothesis (H_{03}) test revealed a weak positive, and statistically significant relationship between repairs/replacements and robustness of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-South Nigeria, with β value of 0.288, suggesting that improvements in Repairs/Replacements are associated with enhanced Robustness. The t-value of 4.330 exceeds the critical value of 1.96 for significance in a two-tailed test, and the p-value of 0.000 confirms statistical significance, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis (H_{03}) and affirm a significant link between Repairs/Replacements and Robustness. Furthermore, the R^2 value of 0.596 indicates that approximately 59.6% of the variance in Robustness is explained by Repairs/Replacements. This finding is not surprising as it agrees with earlier study by Hassan and Huscroft (2021) who found that digitalizing reverse logistics operations significantly improved organizational resilience by enhancing flexibility and responsiveness to market changes.

Relationship between Repairs/Replacements and Flexibility: From figures 3 and 4, and table 7, the results of the hypothesis (H_{04}) test indicated a weak positive, and no significant relationship between repairs/replacements and flexibility of Maritime Logistics Companies in South-

South Nigeria, with β value of 0.125 suggesting a slight association between repairs/replacements and flexibility. The t-value of 1.889 < 1.96 and the p-value of 0.059 > 0.05, leading to a failure to reject the null hypothesis (H_{04}). Additionally, the R^2 value of 0.549 indicates that approximately 54.9% of the variance in flexibility is explained by repairs/replacements. This finding is surprising as it disagrees with Mao, Li, and Chen (2020) who found that effective management of returns and exchanges provided sustainability benefits, especially through resource recovery processes.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that while returns and exchanges contribute positively and significantly to the robustness of these companies, their influence on flexibility is limited and negative. Similarly, repairs and replacements show a weak positive link with robustness but do not significantly enhance flexibility. Overall, the results underscore the importance of enhancing specific reverse logistics practices to improve organizational resilience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Managers of Maritime logistics companies should optimize their returns and exchanges processes to strengthen their robustness further. This could involve effectively managing returns and exchanges to minimize costs and customer dissatisfaction.
2. Given the non-significant relationship between returns/exchanges and flexibility, Management of maritime logistics companies should develop other robust systems and structures that can withstand disruptions rather than solely focusing on returns/exchanges. These strategies may include adopting a flat structure to facilitate quicker decision-making and creating cross-functional teams for collaboration and knowledge sharing.
3. Managers of maritime logistics companies should enhance the adoption of repairs and replacements strategies in order to increase their robustness abilities. This can be achieved by establishing efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.
4. Based on the non-significant relationship between repairs/replacements and flexibility, Management of maritime logistics companies should formulate other strategies of achieving flexibility, such as investing in employee training and development, promoting skill diversification and continuous learning, and allowing staff to adapt to new technologies and roles.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to the existing literature by highlig-

-hting the specific relationships between reverse logistics practices and organizational resilience in the maritime logistics sector, particularly in the context of South-South Nigeria. It provides empirical evidence on how different dimensions of reverse logistics affect organizational robustness and flexibility, thus enriching the understanding of reverse logistics in enhancing resilience.

Suggestion for Further Research

Future research should explore the underlying factors that influence the relationship between reverse logistics practices and flexibility, particularly focusing on external variables such as market conditions, regulatory influences, and technological advancements. Additionally, studies could examine the impact of organizational culture on the effectiveness of reverse logistics practices, offering deeper insights into how maritime logistics companies can enhance their resilience. Expanding the research to include comparative studies across different regions or industries could also provide valuable benchmarks and best practices in reverse logistics and organizational resilience.

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APPENDIX I**QUESTIONNAIRE****REVERSE LOGISTICS PRACTICES AND ORGANISATIONAL RESILIENCE OF MARITIME
LOGISTIC COMPANIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA.**

Please objectively respond to the following questions. Kindly tick the box for demographics in Section (A) and the item questions in Section B, C and D (with any option from strongly agree to strongly disagree as displayed). Kindly respond to all questions, even if they appear repetitive, and please note that there are no right or wrong answers. All information given shall be treated confidentially.

SECTION A:**Respondent's Demographics**

(1) Please state your Gender (a) Male (b) Female

(2) Please state your age bracket (a) 20- 29 (b) 30 - 39 (c) 40 – 49

(d) 50 – 59 (e) 60 and above

(4) Highest educational qualification (a) WAEC/(SSCE)/NECO

(d) NCE/OND (f) HND/ BSC (h) M.Sc./MBA (h) Ph.D/DBA.

Section B

Kindly, indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree that the statement reflects the situation in your organisation.

REVERSE LOGISTICS PRACTICES						
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	RETURNS AND EXCHANGES	5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization effectively manages returns and exchanges to minimize costs and customer dissatisfaction.					
2	In our firms, we have established efficient processes and systems for handling product returns and exchanges.					
3	In our company, customer returns and exchanges are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.					
4	In our organisation, we actively analyze and learn from return and exchange data to identify opportunities for improvement.					
5	Our organization provides clear and transparent return and exchange policies to customers.					
6	Overall, our returns and exchanges processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.					
Source: (Borek & Kratz, 2023; Ghiani & Manni, 2023)						

REPAIRS AND REPLACEMENTS						
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our organization effectively manages repairs and replacements to minimize downtime and costs.					
2	We have established efficient processes and systems for handling product repairs and replacements.					
3	Product repairs and replacements are seamlessly integrated into our overall supply chain operations.					
4	We actively analyze and learn from repair and replacement data to identify opportunities for improvement.					
5	Our organization provides timely and reliable repair and replacement services to customers.					
6	Overall, our repairs and replacements processes contribute positively to customer satisfaction and loyalty.					
Source: Golicic, Smith & Mentzer, 2023; Jenner & Durach, 2023)						

Section C

ORGANISATIONAL RESILIENCE						
S/ N	ROBUSTNESS	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Our company does not give up and continues its path.					
2	Our company stands straight and preserves its position.					
3	Our company is successful in generating diverse solutions					
4	Our company shows resistance to the end in order not to lose.					
Source: (Chu, 2015; Kantur & Iseri-Say, 2015)						

S/ N	FLEXIBILITY	5	4	3	3	1
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Our company is flexible in allocating marketing resources to market a diverse line of products.					
2	Our company is flexible in allocating production resources to manufacture a broad range of product.					
3	Our company is flexible in product design to support a broad range of potential product.					
4	Our company has an ability to adapt our product strategies to match products/ services with targeted market segment.					
5	Our company redeploys organizational resources effectively to support our firm's intended strategies.					
6	Our company modifies the resources we can use in developing, manufacturing, and delivering its intended products to targeted markets.					
Source: (Chu, 2015)						